

Chemical Studies of Heterocyclic Compounds with Pharmacological Possibilities: Isonicotinoyl Hydrazones as Antituberculous Agents

*Hari Singh and Jai Chand Verma

Several hydrazones of isonicotinic acid hydrazide with phenolic aldehydes and ketones have been prepared for studying their antituberculous properties. Their behaviour with copper sulphate, nickel sulphate, and ammoniacal silver nitrate has been studied.

Following the discovery that isonicotinic acid hydrazide¹ (Isoniazid, Rimifon, Nydrazid) possesses antitubercular properties², some other pyridine³ and other hydrazides⁴ were investigated for the purpose and were either found inactive or much less potent.

As a logical step, some compounds having heterocyclic pyridyl nitrogen, like isonicotinaldehyde thiosemicarbazone⁵, a series of *N*²-substituted derivatives⁶ and hydrazones⁷ of isonicotinic acid hydrazide with a variety of aldehydes and ketones were also studied. Some of them were found to possess a high bacteriostatic activity and a limited few, a definite therapeutic value. The corresponding compounds of nicotinic acid were, however, found to be much less active.

During the course of the present investigation, condensation products of isonicotinic acid hydrazide with phenolic aldehydes and ketones have been synthesised with a view to studying their antituberculous activity.

The tuberculostatic property of hydrazides is regarded to have a distinct relation with the formation of sparingly soluble chelates⁸ with copper ions. Presence of a suitably placed hydroxyl group in most of these compounds further enhances their chelate-forming

* Present address: Department of Chemistry, University of Sheffield, Sheffield 10, U.K.

1. Meyer and Mally, *Monatsh.*, 1912, **33**, 393.
2. Bernstein *et al.*, *Amer. Rev. Tuberc.*, 1952, **65**, 357; Steenken and Wolinsky, *ibid.*, 1952, **65**, 365; Domagk *et al.*, *Naturwiss.*, 1952, **39**, 188; Fox, *Science*, 1952, **116**, 129.
3. Offe *et al.*, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1952, **7b**, 462.
4. Buu-Hoi *et al.*, *Compt. rend.*, 1952, **234**, 1925; Offe *et al.*, *Naturwiss.*, 1952, **39**, 118; Grassi *et al.*, *Atti Soc. lombarda Sci. med. biol.*, 1952, **7**, 1; Roth *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1953, **36**, 941; Buu-Hoi *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1358; Buvin *et al.*, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1952, **4**, 844.
5. Grunberg *et al.*, *Disease of Chest*, 1952, **21**, 369.
6. McMillan *et al.*, *J. Amer. Pharam. Assoc.*, 1953, **42**, 457.
7. Domagk *et al.*, *Deut. med. Wochschr.*, 1952, **77**, 573; Shchukins *et al.*, *Doklady Akad. Nauk S. S. S. R.*, 1952, **84**, 981; Cavalline *et al.*, *Farm. Sci. tec. (Pavia)*, 1952, **7**, 138; Mantegazza and Tommasini, *Atti Soc. lombarda Sci. med. biol.*, 1952, **7**, 496; Cavalline *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1952, **7**, 161; Sah and Peoples, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1954, **43**, 513.
8. Buu-Hoi *et al.*, *Compt. rend.*, 1952, **234**, 1925; Peguin, *Lancet*, 1952, **263**, 536; Jeney *et al.*, *Zentral. Bakteriol. Parasitenk. Abt., I Orig.*, 1954, **160**, 677.

property and is likely to increase their tuberculostatic effect. These compounds also offer possibility of being less toxic than the parent hydrazide as a result of the blocking of the free amino group.

The isonicotinoyl hydrazones have been synthesised in about 80-95% yields by condensing isonicotinic acid hydrazide with phenolic aldehydes and ketones in ethanol. The compounds are highly crystalline, colorless to light yellow in colour, insoluble in water, and soluble in dilute alkalis. Solubility of the compounds obtained from the aldehydes, in general, is more in ethanol and acetic acid than those of the ketones. These reduce ammoniacal silver nitrate solution and form coloured precipitates with copper ions (Cu^{2+}). Compounds obtained from *ortho*-hydroxyaldehydes and ketones furnish coloured precipitates with nickel ions (Ni^{2+}) also. The tuberculostatic property of these compounds is under investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Hydroxyketones were prepared by the Fries migration of the respective esters⁹.

3-Nitro-4-hydroxy- and 3-nitro-6-hydroxy-acetophenones were obtained by nitration of *p*-hydroxy- and *o*-hydroxy-acetophenone respectively according to the method described by Joshi and Singh¹⁰.

o-Hydroxyaldehydes. — 2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-, 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-, 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-, 2-hydroxy-3-chloro-, 2-hydroxy-4-chloro-, 2-hydroxy-5-bromo-, and 2-hydroxy-4, 5-dimethyl-benzaldehydes were synthesised by the improved Duff reaction¹¹.

Isonicotinoyl Hydrazones.—An anhydrous ethanolic solution of phenolic aldehyde or ketone and isonicotinic acid hydrazide in equivalent quantities was refluxed on a water bath for 2hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and the precipitated solid was filtered, washed with dilute aqueous ethanol, and recrystallised from a suitable solvent. The compounds prepared are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

S.No.	Carbonyl compound.	%Yield.	M.P.	Behaviour with Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} .		Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1	2-Hydroxy-B	85	a244°	Yellow ppt.	Orange Yellow ppt.	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3$	N : 17.1	17.4
2	3-Hydroxy-B ^c	83	b263°	Faint green colour		$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3$	N : 16.9	17.4
3	4-Hydroxy-B	81	286°	Light green colour		$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3$	N : 17.8	17.4
4	2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-B	85	238°	Light tan ppt.	Dark orange ppt.	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3$	N : 16.2	16.5
5	2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-B	80	253°	Orange-yellow ppt.	Light orange ppt.	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3$	N : 16.8	16.5
6	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-B	81	220°	Dirty yellow ppt.	Orange ppt.	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3$	N : 16.8	16.5
7	2-Hydroxy-4,5-dimethyl-B	90	219°	Light yellow ppt.	Orange ppt.	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3$	N : 15.6	15.0
8	2-Hydroxy-3-chloro-B	83	263°	Dirty yellow ppt.	Orange ppt.	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3\text{Cl}$	N : 15.6	15.2

9. *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 4271.

10. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 4993.

11. Liggett and Diehl, *Proc. Iowa Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 52, 191.

TABLE I (contd.)

S. No.	Carbonyl compound.	% Yield.	M.P.	Behaviour with		Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
				Cu ²⁺ .	Ni ²⁺ .			
9	2-Hydroxy-5-chloro-B ^c	88	241°	Light orange ppt.	Orange ppt.	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	N : 15.7	15.2
10	2-Hydroxy-5-bromo-B ^c	80	253°	Yellowish ppt.	Orange ppt.	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ Br	N : 12.7	13.1
11	4-Hydroxy-5-methoxy-B ^c	84	226°	Light yellow colour	..	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃	N : 15.0	15.5
12	Holeotropin	87	231°	Light yellow colour	..	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃	N : 15.2	15.6
13	4-Methoxy-B	95	164°	Light green colour	..	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃	N : 16.3	16.5
14	2-Hydroxy-A ^c	89	239°	Yellowish brown ppt.	Orange ppt.	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃	N : 17.0	16.5
15	4-Hydroxy-A ^c	85	275°	..	..	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃	N : 16.2	16.5
16	2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-A	82	245°	Dirty yellow ppt.	Orange ppt.	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃	N : 15.3	15.6
17	2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-A	80	206°	Yellowish brown ppt.	Orange ppt.	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃	N : 15.1	15.6
18	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-A	84	236°	Brownish yellow ppt.	Dark orange ppt.	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃	N : 16.0	15.6
19	4-Hydroxy-5-methyl-A	84	237°	Light yellow colour	..	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃	N : 15.1	15.6
20	4-Hydroxy-5-chloro-A	80	267°	Green colour	..	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	N : 14.2	14.5
21	2-Hydroxy-5-chloro-A	86	233°	Yellow ppt.	Light orange ppt.	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	N : 14.1	14.5
22	2-Hydroxy-5-bromo-A	80	231°	Yellow ppt.	Light orange ppt.	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₃ Br	N : 12.4	12.6
23	2-Hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyl-A	82	276°	Yellow ppt.	Light orange ppt.	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ Br	N : 12.4	12.1
24	2-Hydroxy-3-chloro-5-bromo-A	84	273°	Yellow ppt.	Yellow ppt.	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ ClBr	Cl + Br: 30.4	31.3
25	2-Hydroxy-3-bromo-5-chloro-A	85	279°	Dirty yellow ppt.	Light yellow ppt.	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ ClBr	Cl + Br: 30.6	31.3
26	2-Hydroxy-5-nitro-A	80	279°	Light yellow ppt.	Yellow ppt.	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₄	N : 19.2	18.7
27	4-Hydroxy-5-nitro-A	83	250°	Light yellow colour	..	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₄	N : 19.0	18.7
28	2,4-Dihydroxy-A ^c	85	283°	Faint yellow ppt.	Yellowish orange ppt.	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃	N : 15.0	15.5
29	2,5-Dihydroxy-A	82	250°	Light orange ppt.	Orange ppt.	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃	N : 14.9	15.5
30	4-Methoxy-A ^c	85	193°	Bluish green colour	..	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃	N : 15.7	15.6
31	2-Hydroxy-P	80	193°	Yellowish ppt.	Light orange ppt.	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃	N : 15.3	15.6
32	4-Hydroxy-P ^c	80	241°	Faint green colour	..	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃	N : 15.2	15.6

TABLE I (contd.)

S. No.	Carbonyl compound.	%Yield.	M.P.	Behaviour with Cu ²⁺ . Ni ²⁺ .		Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
33.	2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-P	83	213°	Yellow ppt.	Orange ppt.	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃	N : 15.0	14.8
34.	4-Hydroxy-6-methyl-P	85	175°	Faint green colour	..	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃	N : 14.8	14.8
35.	2-Hydroxy-5-chloro-P	82	241°	Yellowish ppt.	Orange ppt.	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	N : 13.4	13.8
36.	2-Hydroxy-5-bromo-P	81	237°	Dirty yellow ppt.	Orange yellow ppt.	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ Br	N : 12.5	12.1

N.B. All compounds have been crystallised from anhydrous ethanol except No. 28 which has been crystallised from a mixture of anhydrous ethanol and acetic acid. All melting points are uncorrected.

B, A, and P denote respectively benzaldehyde, acetophenone, and propiophenone.

a—Lit. m.p. 238-39° (Shchukina *et al.*); 242-45° (Cavalline *et al.*)

b—Lit. m.p. 280-81° (do ()); 285-88° (do ())

c—Lit. m.p. 126-27° (do); 165° (do ())

d—Lit. m.p. 236-38° (Cavalline *et al.*)

e—Reported earlier by Sah and Peoples, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1954, 43, 515.

Behaviour of Isonicotinoyl Hydrazones with Metallic Ions (Cu²⁺ or Ni²⁺).—To an aqueous solution of copper sulphate or nickel sulphate (nearly 0.05M) an excess of the ethanolic solution of isonicotinoyl hydrazone was added. The precipitation or coloration obtained is noted in Table I.

The authors are thankful to the Science Research Committee, Uttar Pradesh, and the Ministry of Scientific Research and Cultural Affairs, Govt. of India, New Delhi, for grants.